

Table 2. Relationship between total amylase activity in the kernel and dry matter accumulation in the rice seedling.^a

Temperature (°C)	Power function formulas	Correlation coefficient
20	$Y = 0.181 X^{0.963}$	$r_{\text{kernel}} = 0.986^{**}$
25	$Y = 0.192 X^{0.917}$	$r_{\text{kernel}} = 0.989^{**}$
30	$Y = 0.185 X^{0.981}$	$r_{\text{kernel}} = 0.989^{**}$
35	$Y = 0.180 X^{1.008}$	$r_{\text{kernel}} = 0.978^{**}$
40	$Y = 0.274 X^{0.729}$	$r_{\text{kernel}} = 0.903^{**}$
30/20	$Y = 0.193 X^{0.914}$	$r_{\text{kernel}} = 0.913^{**}$
30/25	$Y = 0.187 X^{0.813}$	$r_{\text{kernel}} = 0.912^{**}$
35→20 ^b	$Y = 0.182 X^{0.993}$	$r_{\text{kernel}} = 0.980^{**}$

*** = significant at the 1% level. ^aChange in temperature treatment.

pH 5.6 citric acid buffer and starch solution for 5 min. Amylase activity was stopped with 0.4 N NaOH. Solution maltose reacted with 3,5-dinitrosalicylic acid and the reactant was measured with a spectrophotometer.

Greenhouse temperatures were maintained at constants of 20, 25, 30, 35, and 40 °C, alternated between 30/25 °C and 30/20 °C day/night temperature, and changed from 35 °C on day 1 to 20 °C on day 7. All had a 12-h photoperiod.

Varieties responded differently to temperatures, but all showed similar

trends. Data in the tables are therefore only for Lushuang 1011 and Shanyou 63. Amylase activity was associated strongly with seedling growth, especially dry matter accumulation (Table 1). Both amylase activity and dry weight increased with time.

The greater the amylase activity of the kernel, the faster dry weight accumulates in seedlings. A power function, $Y = AX^B$, was used to describe the relationship (Table 2). It is clear from the functions that during the young seedling period, a higher shoot weight

can be obtained by increasing amylase activity of the kernel.

Among the constant temperature treatments, 30 °C was clearly optimum for seedling growth and amylase activity (Table 1). The aim, however, was to transplant seedlings into the field. The temperature difference between greenhouse and field was too great for seedlings to adapt to the cold temperatures of early spring in southern China. The 20 °C treatment was most like the ambient temperature, but seedlings were too short to transplant.

The greatest shoot dry weight, combined with high root-shoot ratio and high amylase activity, was obtained with the change in temperature treatment, which provides warmth for maximum germination and early growth. This is followed by a gradual hardening-off, which seedlings need if they are to adapt to cold temperatures. We recommend this treatment to produce vigorous seedlings that are adapted to field temperatures at transplanting. ■

Variability, heritability, correlation, path analysis, and genetic divergence studies in upland rice

S. S. Mehetre, C. R. Mahajan, P. A. Patil, S. K. Lad, and P. M. Dhumal, Botany Section, College of Agriculture, Kolhapur 416004, Maharashtra, India

We studied the genotypic and phenotypic coefficients of variation, heritability, genetic advancement (GA), coefficients of correlation, path analysis, and genetic divergence of 37 promising upland rice cultivars. The experiment was laid out in a randomized block design during 1992 with two replications.

Analysis of variance showed significant differences among genotypes for all characters (Table 1). Considerable range of variation was expressed for plant height, panicles/m², straw yield/m², grain yield/m², and filled grains/panicle, indicating better scope for genetic improvement in these characters. Grain yield/m² had maximum genotypic

coefficient of variation (GCV) (38.2), followed by straw yield/m² (37.6).

Estimates of heritability ranged from 45.9% for plant height to 96.2% for days to maturity. Even though days to 50% flowering (93.9%) and filled grains/panicle (85.3%) had high heritability, they had low GCV. This might be due to the variation in environmental components involved with these traits.

Expected GA ranged from 9.0% for panicle length to 73.8% for straw yield/m². Filled grains/panicle, productive tillers/m², and plant height showed high GA with high GCV and should be considered for obtaining high genetic gain.

Grain yield/m² was positively and significantly correlated with straw yield/m² ($r = 0.604$) and filled grains/panicle ($r = 0.434$), while it was negatively and significantly correlated with days to 50% flowering ($r = -0.495$) and maturity ($r = -0.405$). Plant height was significantly and positively correlated with straw yield/m² ($r = 0.714$), panicle length ($r = 0.632$) and filled grains/

panicle ($r = 0.355$), while it was significantly and negatively correlated with productive tillers/m² ($r = -0.441$).

Panicle length was significantly and positively correlated with straw yield/m² ($r = 0.547$) and filled grains/panicle ($r = 0.425$). Filled grains/panicle was significantly and positively correlated with straw yield/m² ($r = 0.647$) and grain yield/m² ($r = 0.434$).

Path analysis studies indicated filled grains/panicle extend direct positive influence on grain yield (0.077). This high magnitude of association between the two was because of the positive indirect effect through days to maturity (0.695) and productive tillers/m² (0.114).

Correlation and path analysis studies revealed that filled grains/panicle, plant height, and panicle length were important yield-contributing characters. They should be considered when adopting selection criteria in upland rice breeding programs.

Genetic divergence studies using D² analysis showed that the genotypes fall into seven distinct clusters (Table 2).

Table 1. Genetic parameters of variation in upland rice. Kolhapur, Maharashtra, India, 1992.

Parameter	Characters								
	Days to 50% flowering	Days to maturity	Plant height (cm)	Panicle length (cm)	Productive tillers/m ² (no.)	Filled grains/panicle (no.)	Straw yield/m ² (g)	Grain yield/m ² (g)	
Mean	95.7	124.9	73.9	17.4	297.9	71.8	93.8	60.4	
CV	1.5	1.2	14.6	3.5	10.5	8.3	11.9	14.4	
Range	Minimum	85.0	111.0	57.2	16.5	242.5	38.4	40.0	20.0
	Maximum	106.5	137.0	106.6	19.5	432.5	97.8	195.0	112.5
Variance	(G)	31.5	38.1	98.3	0.8	1378.5	205.7	1244.1	532.0
	(P)	33.6	39.6	214.0	1.2	2350.4	241.1	1368.2	607.7
Coefficient of variance	(G)	5.9	4.9	13.4	5.2	12.5	20.0	37.6	38.2
	(P)	6.1	5.0	19.8	6.3	16.3	21.6	39.4	40.8
Heritability (%)		93.9	96.2	45.9	69.3	58.7	85.3	90.9	87.5
Genetic advancement (% of mean)		11.7	10.0	18.7	9.0	19.7	38.0	73.8	73.6
<i>Coefficients of correlation and path analysis^a</i>									
Days to 50% flowering	<i>r_g^b</i>	-	0.964**	-0.607**	-0.269	0.224	-0.298	-0.361*	-0.495**
	<i>p^c</i>	<u>-2.332</u>	1.525	0.501	-0.072	0.074	-0.072	-0.264	-
Days to maturity	<i>r_g</i>	-	-	-0.467**	-0.210	0.101	-0.245	-0.218	-0.405**
	<i>p</i>	1.581	<u>-2.248</u>	0.385	-0.056	0.034	0.060	-0.159	-
Plant height (cm)	<i>r_g</i>	-	-	-	0.632**	-0.441**	0.355*	0.714**	0.310
	<i>p</i>	-0.824	1.416	<u>-0.738</u>	0.169	-0.147	-0.086	0.521	-
Panicle length (cm)	<i>r_g</i>	-	-	-	-	-0.168	0.425**	0.547**	0.281
	<i>p</i>	0.267	0.626	-0.333	<u>-0.521</u>	-0.056	-0.103	0.400	-
Productive tillers/m ² (no.)	<i>r_g</i>	-	-	-	-	-	0.320	-0.071	0.180
	<i>p</i>	0.332	-0.523	0.160	0.364	<u>-0.045</u>	-0.056	-0.052	-
Filled grains/panicle (no.)	<i>r_g</i>	-	-	-	-	-	-	0.647**	0.434**
	<i>p</i>	-0.243	0.695	-0.388	-0.293	0.114	<u>0.077</u>	0.472	-
Straw yield/m ² (g)	<i>r_g</i>	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	0.604**
	<i>p</i>	0.730	0.842	-0.345	-0.588	0.146	-0.024	<u>-0.157</u>	-

^aResidual effect = 0.2709; underlined figures denote direct effects. * and ** = significant at the 5 and 1% level, respectively. ^b*r_g* = genotypic correlation coefficient. ^c*p* = path coefficient.

Table 2. Genetic divergence^a in 37 genotypes of upland rice. Kolhapur, Maharashtra, India, 1992.

Cluster	Genotype	Areas of cultivation	Days to		Plant height (cm)	Panicle length (cm)	Filled grains/panicle (no.)	Productive tillers/plant (no.)	Straw yield/plant (g)	Grain yield/plant (g)
			50% flowering	Maturity						
			I	II						
I	ACK83-9-1, PBNR87-6, BG380-2, VDN4288, RTN711, R24, Jaya RP4-14, IET6724	Maharashtra (Kolhapur, Pune), Marathwada (Parbhani), Konkan (Ratnagiri), Andhra Pradesh	102.35	131.35	63.31	16.80	68.62	9.50	6.66	11.04
			(7.95)	(10.90)	(14.26)	(20.34)	(8.80)	(14.80)	(21.50)	-
II	PBNR87-8, PBNR87-9, IR36, Pusa 33, K184, PLG39-4-1, Rasi, Ratna, RDN185-2	Marathwada (Parbhani), Western Maharashtra (Kolhapur), Konkan (Ratnagiri), Uttar Pradesh, Orissa, the Philippines	95.66	125.00	63.40	16.86	57.35	9.03	6.87	8.83
			-	(6.94)	(11.67)	(15.95)	(8.67)	(17.35)	(14.34)	-
III	PBNR5, PBNR88-1, PBNR88-2, PBNR88-3, PBNR89-2, PBNR89-4, TP9-3-2, MAU, Prabhvati, Ambemohor local, Terna, Tuljapur 1, Jalgaon 5	Marathwada (Parbhani, Tuljapur), Western Maharashtra (Jalgaon)	91.85	121.85	86.75	17.89	80.06	7.98	11.16	10.16
			-	-	(8.22)	(12.60)	(10.37)	(14.29)	(13.57)	-

continued on next page

Table 2 continued

Cluster	Genotype	Areas of cultivation	Days to		Plant height (cm)	Panicle length (cm)	Filled grains/panicle (no.)	Productive tillers/plant (no.)	Straw yield/plant (g)	Grain yield/plant (g)
			50% flowering I	Maturity II						
IV	PBNR89-6, K35-3	Marathwada (Parbhani), Konkan (Ratnagiri)	86.00 -	112.50 -	77.75 -	18.20 <u>(5.56)</u>	80.70 (15.25)	9.08 (23.55)	9.11 (8.16)	18.68 -
V	PBNR88-4	Marathwada (Parbhani)	98.50 -	127.00 -	71.40 -	19.50 -	86.50 <u>(0.00)</u>	7.59 (14.21)	5.36 (17.71)	9.30 -
VI	Krishna Sal	Western Maharashtra (Ahmednager)	101.00 -	130.00 -	93.40 -	18.70 -	88.40 -	10.08 <u>(0.00)</u>	9.90 (25.02)	22.87 -
VII	Ambika	Marathwada (Parbhani)	85.00 -	113.00 -	83.50 -	16.50 -	52.50 -	58.41 -	12.15 <u>(0.00)</u>	12.22 -
	Pooled mean	-	94.34	123.90	77.67	17.78	74.76	8.80	8.74	13.96

Figures in parentheses are intercluster D values. Underlined figures in parentheses are intracluster D values. Figures without parentheses are mean performance values.

When planning hybridization programs to achieve early flowering and maturity, varieties from Cluster VII (Ambika) may be used; for dwarfness, Clusters I and VI;

for panicle length, Cluster VI (Krishna Sal); for filled grains/panicle, Cluster VI (Krishna Sal); for productive tillers/plant, Cluster IV (PBNR89-6 and K35-3); and

for straw yield/plant, Cluster VII (Ambika). ■

Pest resistance—diseases

Strain differentiation of rice tungro bacilliform virus by restriction fragment length analysis of polymerase chain reaction-amplified products

A. C. Dolores-Talens, J. R. Escara-Wilke, P. Q. Cabauatan, R. J. Nelson, and H. Koganezawa, IRRRI

Tungro is the most important disease of rice in South and Southeast Asia. A composite of two viruses, rice tungro bacilliform virus (RTBV) and rice tungro spherical virus (RTSV), causes the disease. Multiple strains of RTBV, a double-stranded DNA virus, have been reported recently. Each of the strains, L, G1, G2, and Ic, manifests distinct symptoms on rice cultivars FK135 and Taichung Native 1. Strain Ic induced interveinal chlorosis, stunting, reduced tillering, and narrowing of leaves. G1 and G2 induced only mild stunting. The symptoms caused by these strains were not as severe as those manifested by type strain L.

Polymerase chain reaction (PCR) and subsequent restriction enzyme digestion were used to investigate molecular variations among the strains. Specific segments of the viral genome were amplified by PCR using oligonucleotide primers designed on the basis of published sequence data for RTBV.

The amplified region spanned the intergenic region of the virus with the left, or sense strand, primer (5'-TTACAGAAGGATTGTGAACCC-

3') located within open reading frame 2 (ORF2) and the right, or antisense strand, primer (5'-ACTATAGCTCCTGCTGAACTA-3') located within ORF4 (Fig. 1). Using these primers, a 2.4-kb fragment of RTBV DNA was amplified. Standard PCR conditions were used with 1-10 ng total genomic DNA extract of rice plant tissue and 50 pM primers. The amplified products were resolved on a 2% agarose gel and visualized by staining with

1. Map of the RTBV genome, indicating location of primers used and fragment amplified. (ORF = open reading frame, P = protein.)